

Mitochondria-Catalyzed Activation of Anticancer Prodrugs

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Mitochondria mediate electron transport chain (ETC) to power ATP synthase. In cancer cells, the ETC is disturbed leading to leakage of electrons that ultimately results in generation of H₂O₂. This difference between cancer and healthy cells can be used for the design of cancer-specific prodrugs as confirmed in several proof-of-concept studies. Unfortunately, the known prodrugs are either insufficiently cancer cell specific or their activation efficiency is low. In this work, we solved this problem by optimizing the conjugate of a drug camptothecin and a H₂O₂-responsive aminoferrocene to obtain the prodrug C. The multistep reaction of the prodrug C with H₂O₂ is >20-fold more efficient than

that of the parent system. The prodrug is accumulated and activated in mitochondria of cancer cells in a H₂O₂-dependent fashion. The anticancer efficacy towards human ovarian cancer A2780 and monocytic leukemia THP1 cells is improved from 573 and >3000 nM (for prodrug B) to 142 and 479 nM (for prodrug C) correspondingly. Additionally to the excellent activity, the new prodrug is not toxic in vivo to a range of blood (red and white blood cells, neutrophils, monocytes, platelets) and bone marrow cells (monocytes, B and T cells and others) in contrast to camptothecin.

1. Introduction

Chemotherapy is a standard approach in cancer treatment. It involves the use of chemotherapeutics targeting rapidly dividing cancer cells via a variety of mechanisms. For example, camptothecin (cpt-OH) and its derivatives inhibit topoisomerase I, bleomycin induces breaks in double stranded DNA (dsDNA), doxorubicin intercalates dsDNA, cisplatin and oxaliplatin cause cross-linking of dsDNA.^[1] Despite their effectiveness in killing cancer cells, the chemotherapeutics often cause side effects by affecting healthy cells. One of the common side effects is neutropenia, a medical condition characterized by an abnormally low number of neutrophils.^[1]

Cancer cell specificity of chemotherapeutic drugs can be improved by their conversion to prodrugs. The prodrugs remain inactive in healthy cells but are converted to drugs in the reaction with cancer-specific molecules. Our group is especially interested in developing H₂O₂-responsive prodrugs. H₂O₂ is the most chemically stable representative of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Since H₂O₂ acts as a signaling molecule in healthy cells stimulating their proliferation, its homeostatic intracellular concentration is extremely low. In contrast, in cancer cells the proliferation control is lifted, and H₂O₂ constantly produced that leads to its increased intracellular concentration compared to healthy cells.^[2]

The overall H₂O₂ concentration in cancer cells is reported to be in the broad range of 10⁻⁹ to 7 × 10⁻⁶ M depending on the cell type and the intracellular location of a H₂O₂-responsive probe.^[3] The majority of known probes and prodrugs use H₂O₂-responsive triggers based on arylboronic acids. These triggers react with H₂O₂ in a bimolecular reaction with $k_2 = 1.0 \text{ M}^{-1} \times \text{s}^{-1}$.^[4] At the highest detected intracellular H₂O₂ concentration of 7 × 10⁻⁶ M^[3a] half-conversion ($t_{1/2}$) of the prodrugs using boronic acids as H₂O₂-responsive moieties is expected to occur at $t_{1/2} > 25 \text{ h}$ that is too slow for most applications (Figure 1A).

Some intracellular organelles accumulate H₂O₂. They include lysosomes,^[5] endoplasmic reticulum (ER)^[6] and mitochondria.^[7] Further compartmentalization of the H₂O₂ pools occurs in proximity to proteins generating H₂O₂.^[8] Prodrugs designed to accumulate at ROS-rich intracellular sites are exposed to high local concentrations of H₂O₂ that facilitates their efficient activation. This approach has already been demonstrated for prodrugs targeting lysosomes^[5] and the ER.^[6] However, the development of mitochondria-targeting analogues has, thus far, been less successful. Mitochondria is an especially interesting target for anticancer therapy, since these organelles are critical for cancer

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Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.202500054>

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Figure 1. State-of the art: (A) Illustration of the problem (expected slow conversion rate) of bimolecular activation of arylboronic acid-based, H_2O_2 -responsive prodrugs **A** in cells. (B) The mechanism of activation of the previously reported H_2O_2 -responsive camptothecin (cpt-OH) prodrug aggregate **B** in mitochondria of cancer cells.^[7f] This work: the mechanism of activation of the improved prodrug **C** in mitochondria of cancer cells. Structures of intermediates **C_{i2}** and **C_{i3}** formed in the reaction of decomposition of **C_{i1}** to **C_{i4}/H⁺** + are provided in Figure 3D.

cells.^[9] Moreover, electron transport chain (ETC) is poorly functioning in mitochondria of cancer cells that leads to leakage of electrons, which are accepted mostly by oxygen with formation of superoxide anion radical, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$. The latter ROS is dismutated to oxygen and H_2O_2 either spontaneously or in the more efficient reaction catalyzed by superoxide dismutase (SOD). In this way mitochondria of cancer cell act as catalyst by generating many equivalents of H_2O_2 per one organelle.^[7a] Existing prodrugs responsive to mitochondrial H_2O_2 either lack sufficient cancer cell specificity^[7b-e] or fail to achieve effective activation^[7e,f] resulting in poor anticancer outcomes. For example, V. Reshetnikov et al. have reported on conjugates of aminoferrocenes with a triphenylalkylphosphonium moiety $[\text{Ph}_3\text{AlkylP}\sim]^+$ as a mitochondrial carrier.^[7d] These prodrugs exhibit excellent anticancer activity in the low μMolar range, but are toxic towards healthy cells due to the H_2O_2 -independent mitochondrial depolarization caused by the $[\text{Ph}_3\text{AlkylP}\sim]^+$ group. Furthermore, Klemt et al. have reported on the cpt-OH prodrug **B**, which is activated in a series of chemical reactions in mitochondria of cancer cells (Figure 1B).^[7f] The overall yield of these reactions

does not exceed 3% that limits the applicability of the latter system.

In this paper, we addressed the latter problem by developing prodrug **C** (Figure 1C), which is efficiently activated in cancer cells in a reaction mediated by mitochondrial H_2O_2 leading to cancer cells death. Importantly, the prodrug does not affect primary healthy cells including neutrophils in blood and bone marrow. In contrast, the parent drug camptothecin induces strong neutropenia.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design

We identified two reasons of inefficient activation of previously reported prodrug **B** in the presence of H_2O_2 leading to low to moderate anticancer activity in vitro. First, this prodrug is aggregated in aqueous solutions at concentrations above $0.5 \mu\text{M}$, which is the range of its activity.^[7f] The boronic acid moiety in the aggregate is less accessible to H_2O_2 than in the monomer

Figure 2. Energy minimized (DFT-B3LYP) structures of prodrug **C** and intermediate **C_{i4}** (upper plots) and distribution of conformations in **C_{i4}** and its protonated form **C_{i4}/H⁺** by using molecular dynamics (MD) calculations (lower plots). Other experimental details are provided in the [Supporting Information](#).

that slows down the first reaction step in the activation of the prodrug: formation of aminoferrocenium derivative [**B_{i1}**]⁺. Second, the ammonium intermediate **B_{i4}/H⁺** is converted to the active drug **cpt-OH** in a very slow hydrolysis mediated by mitochondrial HO⁻ ions (Figure 1B).

To address these challenges, we replaced the $-\text{CH}_2-(1H-1,2,3\text{-triazolyl})-(\text{CH}_2)_4-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$ fragment in prodrug **B** with a $-(\text{CH}_2)_3-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$ moiety (highlighted in red in Figure 1C), resulting in prodrug **C**. This modification eliminates the 1H-1,2,3-triazolyl group, which is known to reduce the solubility of aminoferrocene derivatives in aqueous buffers.^[5b,6,7e] Consequently, we anticipated that this substitution would decrease the tendency of the prodrug to aggregate, thereby enhancing its reactivity with H₂O₂. To visualize the structure of prodrug **C**, we conducted its energy minimization by DFT-B3LYP as described in detail in the [Supporting Information](#) (Figure 2). We found that all bond lengths and angles are in the normal range in the energy-minimized structure indicating that all functional components of prodrug **C** are well accommodated in space despite the shortened linker between the drug and the triggering moiety.

The linker in prodrug **C** was designed to facilitate the conversion of the expected amine intermediate **C_{i4}** to the active drug **cpt-OH** through a favorable five-membered transition state. In this state, the nucleophilic -NH₂ group attacks the electrophilic carbon atom in the C=O group (Figure 1C). This intramolecular reaction was expected to be more efficient than the corresponding intermolecular hydrolysis of intermediate **B_{i4}/H⁺** derived from the known prodrug **B**^[7d] (Figure 1B). By using molecular dynamic (MD) calculations, we explored possible conformations of intermediates **C_{i4}** and its protonated form **C_{i4}/H⁺**. We found that the **C_{i4}** forms more compact conformations than its protonated form with the shortest distance between a nitrogen

Scheme 1. Synthesis of prodrug **C**: (a) 4-bromobutane acid methyl ester, Cs₂CO₃, CsI in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF); (b) 1. LiOH in tetrahydrofuran (THF)/water mixture, 2. NaHSO₄; (c) camptothecin (**cpt**-OH), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP), CH₂Cl₂; (d) [1,1'-bis(diphenylphosphino)ferrocenyl]dichloropalladium(II) (Pd(dppf)Cl₂), bis(pinacolato)diboron; CH₃CO₂K. Structures of control compounds **6** and **7** are shown in the inset.

atom of the NH₂ and a carbon atom of the exocyclic C=O around 3 Å (Figure 2). These modelling data confirm the possibility of the intramolecular attack of the nucleophilic -NH₂ group to the electrophilic carbon atom in the C=O group, which is in agreement with Baldwin's rules.

2.2. Synthesis

N-alkylated aminoferrocene-based prodrugs are usually prepared by alkylation of 4-(*N*-ferrocenylaminocarbonyloxymethyl)phenylboronic acid pinacol ester in the presence of a base (Cs₂CO₃ or NaH) and the corresponding alkyl chloride, bromide or iodide.^[5b,6,7c-f] However, the alkylation agent **cpt-O-C(=O)-(CH₂)₃-X** (where X = Cl or I), required for the synthesis of prodrug **C** by this method, could not be coupled under the standard conditions due to its low reactivity and formation of the large number of unexpected side products. Therefore, the synthetic approach was adjusted as outlined in Scheme 1. The new approach is based on the recently published protocol for conversion of aminoferrocene precursors with aryl bromide moiety to the prodrugs by using Miyaura borylation.^[10] Its key advantage is the possibility of introduction of the sensitive boronic acid pinacol ester at the last synthetic step with high yield.

In the first step, intermediate **1**^[10] was alkylated with 4-bromobutane acid methyl ester in the presence of Cs₂CO₃ and CsI to obtain **2** with 46% yield that was followed by hydrolysis of **2** in the presence of LiOH to obtain **3** with 95% yield. The following acylation of **cpt-OH** with **3** in the presence of the activating agent 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) and base 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) furnished **4** with 34% yield. Finally, the prodrug **C** was prepared by borylation of precursor **4** as previously described.^[10] The yield of the last step was 48%. After chromatography the final product was obtained at > 95% purity as confirmed by elemental C, H, N analysis. The product identity was confirmed by 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry.

Figure 3. (A) UV–visible spectra of the prodrug C (0–50 μM) in RPMI 1640 medium containing FBS (5%, m/v) and DMSO (1%, v/v). A zoomed in area between 600 and 900 nm is shown in inset (B). Dependence of absorbance at 789 nm (plot C) and 340 nm (plot D) from the concentration of solutions of prodrug C either in the RPMI 1640/FBS medium defined above (indicated as “RPMI” in the plot) or TEAA buffer (100 mM, pH 7.4, indicated as “TEAA” in the plot). (E,F) Dynamic light scattering (DLS) data obtained for solutions/suspensions of either prodrug C (plot E) or prodrug B (plot F) in the RPMI 1640/FBS medium. Student’s t test: $p \geq 0.05$: ns; $p < 0.001$: ***. Mean values are compared with those of a reference: indicated as “ref”.

Synthesis of control **6** was conducted by using the standard approach as described in the experimental section. Control **7** and prodrug **B** are known compounds, prepared as previously described.^[7f,11]

2.3. Properties of Prodrug C

UV–visible spectra of prodrug C dissolved in the RPMI 1640 medium containing fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%, m/v) and DMSO (1%, v/v) at concentrations 0–10 μM feature a broad peak at 367 nm corresponding the camptothecin chromophore (Figure 3A). Expectedly, no absorbance bands are observed between 600 and 900 nm (Figure 3B). At concentrations $>10 \mu\text{M}$, the baseline absorbance is increased between 600 and 900 nm that corresponds to light reflection on aggregates of prodrug C (Figures 3B,C). The dependence of absorbance at 340 nm (a shoulder of the absorbance band of camptothecin) from prodrug C concentration is linear in the whole range from 0 to 50 μM in the RPMI medium indicating that the monomer and the aggregate/aggregates have similar extinction coefficients at 340 nm (Figure 3D). It is apparent that proteins in FBS favor monomeric prodrug C: compare the data for the FBS-containing RPMI-medium and the FBS-free triethylammonium acetate buffer (TEAA) in Figure 3C.

By using dynamic light scattering (DLS), we directly confirmed prodrug C aggregation at concentrations $> 10 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure 3E). In contrast to the prodrug C, which is soluble in aqueous buffers and not aggregated at the concentration $\leq 10 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure 3A–E), the prodrug B aggregates already at the concentration above 0.5 μM .^[7f] We additionally confirmed that by using DLS: compare the data shown in Figures 3E,F for the prodrugs at 15 μM .

Lipophilicity of prodrug C is rather high, logP 6.06. However, this is not reflected in its low solubility or aggregation in the low micromolar concentration range.

2.4. Reaction of Prodrug C With H_2O_2 in Cell Free Settings

Prodrug C is a conjugate of the fluorescent cpt-OH drug and the aminoferrocene moiety, which is a fluorescence quencher acting via the photoinduced electron transfer (PET) mechanism.^[7f] Correspondingly, the solution of prodrug C (10 μM) in the TEAA buffer is practically not fluorescent (Figure 4A). Under the selected conditions the prodrug C exists as a monomer (Figure 3). Therefore, the quenching is not due to the aggregation. Upon addition of H_2O_2 (2 mM) a series of intermediates ($[\text{C}_i]^\pm$, C_i4/H^\pm , C_i4) and the final product cpt-OH are expected to be formed, which contain either the oxidized aminoferrocene or no ferrocene (Figure 1).

PET is not operative in these cases, therefore, such intermediates are fluorescent. In agreement with the above analysis, the fluorescence of the prodrug C is increased in the presence of H_2O_2 . Importantly, the prodrug C reacts with H_2O_2 substantially faster than with the aggregated prodrug B: compare data in Figure 4A,B. In the absence of H_2O_2 , the fluorescence of the prodrug C is slightly increased that indicates the undesired side reaction or reactions.

To get the more detailed information on the reaction of prodrug C with H_2O_2 as well as its background transformation in the absence of H_2O_2 , we used high performance liquid chromatography (LC) coupled to a UV-absorbance (UV) and mass spectral (MS) detectors (Figure 4C, Figure S46, Supporting Information). We observed no cpt-OH formation in the absence of H_2O_2 after 4 h incubation. The sensitivity of the latter assay does not allow detecting cpt-OH at concentrations $< 0.2 \mu\text{M}$ that would correspond to 1% prodrug C conversion. In contrast, the fluorescence assay described above is highly sensitive and, therefore, can detect even minor side reactions. Based on the combined fluorescence and LC-UV-MS data, we conclude that in the absence of H_2O_2 the prodrug C forms less than 1% cpt-OH within 4 h incubation in the aqueous buffer. In contrast, in the presence of H_2O_2 a major fraction corresponding to cpt-OH was detected, which corresponds to 24% conversion of the prodrug C. Since the product distribution is practically the same at both 4 and 7.5 h incubation, we conclude that the reaction is complete at latest after 4 h incubation. We also detected three stable side products. Two of them correspond to alkylation of C_i1 and C_i4 with para-quinone methide QM (Figure 1): C_i2 and C_i5 , correspondingly. The third one corresponds to the ferrocene decomposition intermediate C_i3 (Figure 4D). The similar intermediates were

Figure 4. (A,B) Fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 436 \text{ nm}$) of solutions of prodrugs C (plot A) and (B) (plot B) (each $10 \mu\text{M}$) in the TEAA buffer without or with H_2O_2 (2 mM). (C) Monitoring the reaction of prodrugs C ($20 \mu\text{M}$, gradient A) and B ($20 \mu\text{M}$, gradient B) with H_2O_2 (10 mM) at pH 7 by using LC-UV-MS: detection of absorbance at 330 nm and identification of the fractions by mass spectrometry (positive mode). Gradients A and B are described in the experimental section. (D) Structures of stable intermediates detected by LC-UV-MS in the solutions of prodrug C.

observed during the decomposition of prodrug B as previously described.^[7] In contrast to prodrug C, prodrug B forms $< 1\%$ cpt-OH after its incubation with H_2O_2 for 4 and 7.5 h (Figure 4C).

2.5. Mechanism of Anticancer Activity and Anticancer Efficacy of Prodrug C in Vitro

We selected human ovarian cancer A2780 cells and human monocytic leukocytes THP1 for studies of ROS-mediated intracellular activation of prodrug C. The level of mitochondrial ROS

Figure 5. (A) The level of mitochondrial ROS (mROS) in different cancer (A2780, THP1) and healthy (GM01379) normalized to cell surface area of the corresponding cells. (B–E) Fluorescence microscopy of A2780 cells co-incubated with mitochondria staining dye R123 and the prodrug C for 60 min. R123 was detected at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 430\text{--}510 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 475\text{--}575 \text{ nm}$ (image C), whereas prodrug C and products of its reaction with mROS in cells were detected at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 420\text{--}470 \text{ nm}$ (without *N*-acetylcysteine-image B), with NAC (+NAC)- image (E). (D) Merge of B and C, Pearson's coefficient: 0.76. (F) Quantification of signal densities in images (B) and (E). Student's t test: $p < 0.001$ –***.

in these cells is very high as determined by using a MitoSox probe (Figure 5A). As negative control cells, we used human lung fibroblasts GM01379, which in contrast to A2780 and THP1 cells, contain very low level of mROS (Figure 5A). Thus, prodrug C should be activated in A2780 and THP1 cells but remain intact and inactive in GM01379 cells providing the mROS play a role in this process.

For one of the mROS-rich cells (A2780), we evaluated distribution of prodrug C and derived from this compound fluorescent species within the cells by using fluorescence microscopy: monitoring the cpt-fluorophore-containing species at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 420\text{--}470 \text{ nm}$. We found that these species co-localize with a mitochondria-specific probe R123 (Pearson's coefficient: 0.76, Figure 5B–D) indicating that they accumulate in mitochondria of A2780 cells. This experiment indicates that the activation of prodrug C and the formation of its derivative products by mROS is possible (Figure 1). Next, we observed that in the presence of the ROS-scavenger *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC), the intensity of the cpt-derived fluorescence signal is significantly reduced (Figure 5E,F), which directly confirms the involvement of mROS in the activation of prodrug C.

Further, we studied the effect of the prodrug C on the viability of the cells by using the MTT assay (Table 1).

IC_{50} values of the prodrug C for mROS-rich cells A2780 and THP1 are 142 ± 68 and $479 \pm 32 \text{ nM}$ correspondingly, whereas the IC_{50} value mROS-deficient cells GM01379 is $>3000 \text{ nM}$. Importantly, the anticancer efficacy for the new prodrug is 4.0 (for A2780 cells) to >6.3 -fold (for THP1 cells) higher than that for the previously reported prodrug B that is in agreement with the higher reactivity of the prodrug C with H_2O_2 in cell free settings (Figure 3). As expected, control 6, where the H_2O_2 -responsive boronic acid pinacol ester moiety is replaced with a chemically stable fluorine atom, exhibits substantially lower anticancer

Compound	Cell Lines ^{b)} /Status of H ₂ O ₂ level ^{c)}		
	A2780/H ₂ O ₂ ⁺	THP1/H ₂ O ₂ ⁺	GM01379/H ₂ O ₂ ⁻
prodrug B (reference)	573 ± 171	>3000	>3000
prodrug C	142 ± 68	479 ± 32	>3000
neg. control 6	2930 ± 1700	–	–
neg. control 7	>3000	–	–
pos. control cpt-OH	6.7 ± 0.6	47 ± 11	–

a) Incubation time: 72 h.
b) A2780: human ovarian cancer cells; THP1: human monocytic leukocytes; GM01379: human lung fibroblasts.
c) "H₂O₂⁺": High intracellular level of H₂O₂; "H₂O₂⁻": Low intracellular level of H₂O₂.

Figure 6. (A) Cell cycle distribution of A2780 cells treated for 48 h either with DMSO (1%, v/v), the prodrug **C** (250 nM) or cpt-OH (20 nM). (B) Quantification of the cell cycle data shown in (A). G0G1/(S + G2) – the number of cells in phases G0 and G1 divided by the number of cells in phases S and G2. Student's t test: $p < 0.001$ –***.

activity towards A2780 cells: $IC_{50} \sim 3000$ nM (Table 1). Similarly, control **7**, where the critical for the activity of the cpt-OH secondary HO-group is protected as a stable in cells carboxylic acid ester, is practically inactive: $IC_{50} > 3000$ nM, Table 1. Collectively these data confirm that the prodrug **C** is activated by ROS in mitochondria of cancer cells.

As previously reported,^[7f] the drug cpt-OH induces cell cycle arrest in G2 phase (Figure 6A). We observed the same cellular phenotype in A2780 cells treated with the prodrug **C** (Figure 6A,B). These data are in agreement with the release of cpt-OH from the prodrug **C** in cells.

Though the prodrug **C** is more active than the previously known **B**, its anticancer efficacy is still lower than that of cpt-OH (Table 1). One of the reasons can be its incomplete activation in cells due to the alternative conversion to stable and inactive side products as observed in cell free settings (Figure 4C,D).

Figure 7. (A) Design of the in vivo experiment (WT = wild type). (B) Weight loss (% relative to the initial animal weight) in carrier (N = 4) and prodrug **C** (N = 3) – treated groups. (C) The number of primary cells isolated from blood or bone marrow of the carrier group was taken for 100%. The numbers of the cells from the prodrug-treated group are calculated relative to the carrier group. All differences between the groups are not statistically significant (Student's t test, $p \geq 0.05$).

2.6. Toxicity of Prodrug C

Wild type mice were injected with prodrug **C** (12mg/kg) three times according to the experimental design indicated in Figure 7A. We did not detect any adverse effects of the prodrug during the experiment. Moreover, no significant reduction of weight of the animals was observed (Figure 7B). On day 7, we compared the number of different primary cells isolated from blood or bone marrow of the prodrug-treated and carrier-treated animals (Figure 7C). The cells from blood were monitored using an automated hemocounter and those from bone marrow – using flow cytometry. The blood cells included: red blood cells (RBC), white blood cells (WBC), neutrophils, monocytes, platelets. The bone marrow cells included monocytes, B cells, T cells, mature neutrophils (M. Neutrophils), immature neutrophils (Im. Neutrophils) as well as in immature bone marrow cells: LineageNEG Sca-1 + c-Kit+ (LSK) and myeloid progenitor (MP) cells. No statistically significant differences were observed between the groups. These data indicate excellent in vivo tolerance of prodrug **C**.

3. Conclusion

We optimized prodrug **B** in this work.^[7d] Its key drawbacks are low solubility in aqueous buffers, proneness to aggregation at < 0.5 μ M and low reactivity with H₂O₂. These properties are reflected in the low activation efficacy of the previously reported prodrug in cancer cells leading to poor anticancer activity. We replaced the linker “–CH₂–(1*H*-1,2,3-triazolyl)–(CH₂)₄–C(=O)–” connecting the drug moiety (cpt-OH) with the H₂O₂-responsive moiety (aminoferrocene) with a shorter linker –(CH₂)₃–C(=O)– to obtain the prodrug **C**. This prodrug is soluble in aqueous buffers and not aggregated in aqueous solutions up to 10 μ M.

The efficacy of the cpt-OH release from the prodrug in the presence of H₂O₂ in cell free settings is >20-fold higher than that for the parent system. In cells, the prodrug **C** is accumulated in mitochondria and reacts with mitochondrial ROS forming cpt-OH. The released cpt-OH induces cell cycle arrest in the G2 phase that leads to cell death. The prodrug accumulation and activation are inhibited by the treatment with the ROS scavenger *N*-acetylcysteine indicating that these processes are H₂O₂-dependent. We found that A2780 and THP1 cells rich in mitochondrial ROS are more sensitive to the prodrug than mROS-poor cells GM013179. Moreover, the prodrug is not toxic towards a range of healthy primary cells (known to have very low level of mitochondrial ROS) *in vivo*. These cells include blood cells—red and white blood cells, neutrophils, monocytes, platelets and bone marrow cells – monocytes, B cells, T cells, mature and immature neutrophils as well as immature bone marrow cells (LineageNEG Sca-1 + c-Kit + and myeloid progenitor cells). All these data provide the strong evidence that the prodrug's mode of action relies on the activation by mitochondrial ROS, which occurs only in cancer, but not healthy cells. Thus, the prodrug **C** is an interesting candidate for further preclinical and clinical development, which exhibits high anticancer efficacy and cancer cell specificity.

4. Experimental Section

Commercially available chemicals of the best quality from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany), Abcr GmbH (Karlsruhe, Germany), Thermo Fisher Scientific (Erlangen, Germany) and BLD Pharmatech GmbH (Reinbek, Germany) were obtained and used without purification. NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance 300, Bruker Avance 400 or Bruker Avance 600 MHz spectrometer. Electropray ionization (ESI) or atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker ESI MicroTOF II focus or a Bruker maXis 4G. Elemental analysis (C, H, and N) was performed in the microanalytical laboratory of the chemical institutes of the Friedrich-Alexander-University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany. The purity of the compounds used in the biological assays was determined by elemental C, H and N analysis. According to these data, the purity was greater than 95%. UV-visible spectra were measured on a Cary 100 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies) by using quartz glass cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. All experiments were performed in triplicate or more, unless otherwise specified. Statistical analyses were conducted using Student's *t* test, if not stated otherwise. Statistical significance was defined as *p* < 0.05; *p* ≥ 0.05 (non-significant, ns), *p* < 0.05 (*); *p* < 0.01 (**); *p* < 0.001 (***). The data were processed and analyzed with Microsoft Excel and Origin 2024. An LC-UV-MS with a Macherey–Nagel EC HPLC NUCLEODUR C18 HTec, 5 μm, 50 × 2 mm column that was coupled to a UV detector and a quadrupole electropray mass spectrometric detector (detection of positively charged ions in the *m/z* range of 300–1200) was applied.

4.1. Synthesis and Characterization of the Prodrugs and Controls

Synthesis of new compounds is described below. Characterization data including numbering of atoms in the prepared compounds are provided in the [Supporting Information](#).

Compound 2: A mixture of **1** (4.87 g, 11.8 mmol, 1.0 eq.), Cs₂CO₃ (11.5 g, 35.3 mmol, 3.0 eq.), CsI (9.32 g, 35.8 mmol, 3.0 eq.) and dry *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 50 mL) was stirred for 5 min and methyl 4-bromobutyrate (2.76 g, 15.2 mmol, 1.92 mL, 1.3 eq.) was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 3 days at 40 °C. Then, the volatile was removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar) and the crude – purified via flash column chromatography (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂/cyclohexane = 5/95 → 60/40, v/v). The product was isolated as brown oil (2.80 g, 5.44 mmol, 46%). TLC: R_f (cyclohexane/CH₂Cl₂ = 20/80, v/v) = 0.17. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ [ppm] = 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H, 1); 7.28 (m, 1H, 2); 7.25 (m, 1H, 2); 5.14 (s, 2H, 3); 4.48 (bs, 2H, 4); 4.12 (s, 5H, 5); 4.01 (t, 2H, ³J (H,H) = 2.0 Hz, 6); 3.74–3.69 (m, 5H, 7/8); 2.37 (t, 2H, ³J (H,H) = 7.1 Hz, 9); 2.07–1.97 (m, 2H, 10). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 101 MHz): δ [ppm] = 135.6 (12); 131.9 (1); 130.0 (2); 122.3 (13); 69.2 (5); 66.9 (3); 64.8 (6); 51.8 (7); 31.2 (9); 23.9 (10). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 4, 8, 11, 14 and 15 were not detectable. High resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS, APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₂₃H₂₅BrFeNO₄ [M + H]⁺ (*m/z*): 514.0311, found: 514.0335. Characterization data: Figures [S1–S6](#), Supporting Information.

Compound 3: Compound **2** (2.05 g, 3.99 mmol, 1.0 eq.) was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (THF, 35 mL) and a mixture of LiOH·H₂O (1.60 mg, 38.1 mmol, 10 eq.) and H₂O (35 mL) was added. The resulting reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 22 °C. Afterwards, THF was removed *in vacuo* (1 mbar). Subsequently, the mixture was acidified to pH = 1 with NaHSO₄, CH₂Cl₂ (40 mL) added, and the aqueous phase extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (4 × 30 mL). The combined organic phases were washed with H₂O (50 mL) and dried over MgSO₄. The volatiles were removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar) resulting in an orange/brownish oil (1.90 mg, 3.80 mmol, 95%). TLC, R_f (cyclohexane/EtOAc = 20/80, v/v) = 0.58. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H, 1); 7.28 (m, 1H, 2); 7.25 (m, 1H, 2); 5.14 (s, 2H, 3); 4.45 (bs, 2H, 4); 4.13 (s, 5H, 5); 4.03–4.02 (m, 2H, 6); 3.77–3.73 (m, 2H, 7); 2.43 (t, 2H, ³J (H,H) = 7.1 Hz, 8); 2.06–2.01 (m, 2H, 9). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 101 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 178.7 (10); 135.4 (11); 131.9 (1); 130.0 (2); 122.3 (12); 69.3 (5); 66.9 (3); 64.9 (6); 31.2 (8); 23.64 (9). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 7, 13 and 14 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₂₂H₂₃BrFeNO₄ [M + H]⁺ (*m/z*) 500.0154, found: 500.0165. Characterization data: Figures [S7–S12](#), Supporting Information.

Compound 4: Camptothecin (cpt-OH) (1.14 g, 3.27 mmol, 1.0 eq.), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP, 1.20 g, 9.82 μmol, 3.0 eq.) and compound **3** (1.84 mg, 3.68 mmol, 1.1 eq.) were dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (60 mL), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC, 1.44 g, 9.28 mmol, 1.63 mL, 3.0 eq.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 22 h. The volatiles were removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar). The crude product was purified via flash column chromatography (SiO₂, ethyl acetate/cyclohexane = 30/70 → 60/40, v/v) yielding a yellow solid (914 mg, 1.10 mmol, 34%). TLC, R_f (cyclohexane/EtOAc = 20/80, v/v) = 0.43. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 8.35 (s, 1H, 1); 8.22–8.19 (m, 1H, 2); 7.94–7.92 (m, 1H, 3); 7.85–7.81 (m, 1H, 4); 7.69–7.65 (m, 1H, 5); 7.48–7.45 (m, 2H, 6); 7.24–7.21 (m, 3H, 7); 5.72 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.1 Hz, 8); 5.43 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.3 Hz, 8); 5.30–5.25 (m, 2H, 9); 5.11 (s, 2H, 10); 4.40 (bs, 2H, 11); 3.99 (s, 5H, 12); 3.93 (m, 2H, 13); 3.73–3.65 (m, 2H, 14); 2.65–2.52 (m, 2H, 15); 2.33–2.25 (m, 1H, 16); 2.19–2.14 (m, 1H, 16); 2.04–2.00 (m, 2H, 17); 0.99 (t, 3H, ³J (H,H) = 7.6 Hz, 18). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 151 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 172.2 (19); 167.7 (20); 157.5 (21); 152.5 (22); 149.0 (23); 146.5 (24); 146.0 (25); 135.5 (26); 131.8 (6); 131.3 (1); 130.8 (4); 129.9 (7); 129.8 (2); 128.6 (27); 128.4 (3); 128.3 (28); 128.2 (5); 122.3 (29); 120.5 (30); 96.0 (7); 76.2 (31); 69.0 (12); 67.3 (8); 66.8 (10); 64.7 (13); 64.6 (13); 50.1 (9); 32.0 (16); 31.1 (15); 22.8 (17); 7.7 (18). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 11, 14, 32 and 33 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₄₂H₃₇BrFeN₃O₇ [M + H]⁺ (*m/z*): 830.1159, found: 830.1168. Characterization data: Figures [S13–S18](#), Supporting Information.

Prodrug C: A mixture of **4** (914 mg, 1.1 mmol, 1.0 eq.), [1,1'-bis-(diphenylphosphino)ferrocen]dichloropalladium(II) (Pd(dppf)Cl₂, 126 mg, 172 μmol, 0.16 eq.), bis(pinacolato)diboron (3.2 mg, 1.27 mmol, 1.15 eq.), potassium acetate (330 mg, 330 mmol, 3.1 eq.) in 1,4-dioxane (5.5 mL) was prepared and stirred at 80 °C for 18 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar). The crude product was purified via flash column chromatography (SiO₂, ethyl acetate/cyclohexane = 50/50 → 75/25, v/v) and subsequent recrystallization from Et₂O. The prodrug **C** was obtained as yellow powder (460 mg, 58.5 μmol, 48%). TLC, R_f (cyclohexane/EtOAc = 20/80, v/v) = 0.43. n-Octanol/water partition coefficient (LogP) = 6.06 ± 0.09. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 601 MHz, 40°C): δ [ppm] = 8.33 (s, 1H, 1); 8.22–8.20 (m, 1H, 2); 7.92–7.91 (m, 1H, 3); 7.83–7.81 (m, 1H, 4); 7.80–7.79 (m, 2H, 5); 7.67–7.64 (m, 1H, 6); 7.36–7.34 (m, 2H, 7); 7.23 (s, 1H, 8); 5.72 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.3 Hz, 9); 5.43 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.3 Hz, 9); 5.28–5.15 (m, 4H, 10/11); 4.41 (bs, 2H, 12); 3.98 (s, 5H, 13); 3.91–3.90 (m, 2H, 14); 3.76–3.66 (m, 2H, 15); 2.64–2.52 (m, 2H, 16); 2.32–2.28 (m, 1H, 17); 2.20–2.15 (m, 1H, 17); 2.07–2.02 (m, 2H, 18); 1.34 (s, 12H, 19); 0.99 (t, 3H, ³J (H,H) = 7.6 Hz, 20). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 151 MHz, 40°C): δ [ppm] = 172.2 (21); 167.6 (22); 157.5 (23); 152.6 (24); 149.1 (25); 146.6 (26); 146.1 (27); 139.5 (28); 135.2 (6); 131.2 (1); 130.8 (5); 129.9 (2); 128.7 (29); 128.4 (30); 128.3 (3); 128.2 (6); 127.3 (7); 120.6 (31); 96.1 (8); 84.0 (32); 76.2 (33); 69.0 (13); 67.6 (11); 67.3 (9); 64.7 (14); 64.6 (14); 50.1 (10); 32.1 (17); 31.3 (16); 25.1 (19); 23.7 (18); 7.7 (20). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 15, 34, 35 and 36 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₄₈H₄₉BFeN₃O₉ [M + H]⁺ (m/z): 878.2906, found: 878.2914. Elemental analysis: calcd (%) for C₄₈H₄₉BFeN₃O₉: C 65.70, H 5.51, N 4.79; found: C 65.68, H 5.43, N 5.00. Characterization data: Figures S19–S24, Supporting Information.

4-[N-Ferrocenyl-N-(4-fluorophenylmethyloxycarbonyl)amino]butane acid methyl ester (S1): A mixture of **5** (80.0 mg, 227 μmol, 1.0 eq.), Cs₂CO₃ (226 mg, 694 μmol, 3.1 eq.), CsI (182 μmol, 701 μmol, 3.1 eq.) and dry DMF (1 mL) was prepared and stirred for 5 min. Then, 4-bromobutaneacid methyl ester (74.0 mg, 51.0 μL, 409 μmol, 1.8 eq.) was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 3 days at 40 °C. Afterwards, the volatiles were removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar) and the obtained crude product was purified via column chromatography (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂). The product was isolated as brown oil (76.2 mg, 168 μmol, 74%). TLC, R_f (CH₂Cl₂) = 0.28. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 7.40–7.36 (m, 2H, 1); 7.08–7.04 (m, 2H, 2); 5.16 (s, 2H, 3); 4.48 (bs, 2H, 4); 4.11 (s, 5H, 5); 4.01–4.00 (m, 2H, 6); 3.73–3.69 (m, 5H, 7/8); 2.39–2.35 (m, 2H, 9); 2.05–1.97 (m, 2H, 10). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 101 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 173.6 (11); 162.7 (d, J_{C-F} = 248 Hz, 12); 132.3 (13); 130.3 (d, J_{C-F} = 8.4 Hz, 2); 115.6 (d, J_{C-F} = 21.5 Hz, 1); 69.2 (5); 66.9 (3); 64.7 (6); 51.8 (7); 31.2 (9); 23.8 (10). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 8, 14 and 15 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₂₃H₂₄FFeNO₄ [M]⁺ (m/z): 453.1033 found: 453.1036. Characterization data: Figures S25–S30, Supporting Information.

4-[N-Ferrocenyl-N-(4-fluorophenylmethyloxycarbonyl)amino]butane acid (S2): **S2** (230 mg, 507 μmol, 1.0 eq.) was dissolved in THF (5.5 mL) and a mixture of LiOH·H₂O (188 mg, 4.48 mmol, 8.8 eq.) and H₂O (5.5 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 22 °C. Afterwards, THF was removed *in vacuo* (1 mbar) and the mixture was acidified to pH = 1 with NaHSO₄. Subsequently, CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL) was added, and the aqueous phase was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 10 mL). The combined organic phases were washed with H₂O (16 mL) and dried over MgSO₄. The volatiles were removed *in vacuo* (0.01 mbar) resulting in an orange/brownish oil (210 mg, 478 μmol, 94%). TLC, R_f (cyclohexane/EtOAc = 20/80, v/v) = 0.60. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 7.40–7.36 (m, 2H, 1); 7.08–7.04 (m, 2H, 2); 5.16 (s, 2H, 3); 4.45 (bs, 2H, 4); 4.12 (s, 2H, 5); 4.02 (m, 2H, 6); 3.76–3.73 (m, 2H, 7); 2.45–2.41 (m, 2H, 8); 2.04–2.01 (m, 2H, 9). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 101 MHz, rt):

δ [ppm] = 162.8 (d, J_{C-F} = 247 Hz, 11); 132.3 (12); 130.3 (d, J_{C-F} = 8.4 Hz, 2); 115.7 (d, J_{C-F} = 21.4 Hz, 1); 69.3 (5); 67.1 (3); 64.8 (6); 31.2 (8); 23.7 (9). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 4, 7, 10, 13 and 14 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₂₂H₂₃FFeNO₄ [M + H]⁺ (m/z): 440.0955 found: 440.0960. Characterization data: Figures S31–S36, Supporting Information.

Control 6: Camptothecin (cpt-OH, 159 mg, 456 μmol, 1.0 eq.), DMAP (155 mg, 1.27 mmol, 2.8 eq.) and **S2** (200 mg, 455 μmol, 1.0 eq.) were dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (8 mL). EDC (193 mg, 481 μL, 1.24 mmol, 2.7 eq.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 17 h. The volatiles were removed under reduced pressure. Afterwards, the crude product was purified via flash column chromatography (SiO₂, ethyl acetate/cyclohexane = 30/70 → 70/30, v/v) yielding control **6** as yellow solid (60.2 mg, 78.2 μmol, 17%). TLC, R_f (cyclohexane/DCM = 20/80) = 0.17. ¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 8.36 (s, 1H, 1); 8.22–8.19 (m, 1H, 2); 7.94–7.92 (m, 1H, 3); 7.85–7.81 (m, 1H, 4); 7.69–7.65 (m, 1H, 5); 7.36–7.33 (m, 2H, 6); 7.72 (s, 1H, 7); 7.05–7.01 (m, 2H, 8); 5.72 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.1 Hz, 9); 5.43 (d, 1H, ²J (H,H) = 17.1 Hz, 9); 5.25–5.15 (m, 2H, 10); 5.13 (s, 2H, 11); 4.40 (bs, 2H, 12); 3.97 (s, 5H, 13); 3.93–3.91 (m, 2H, 14); 3.72–3.64 (m, 2H, 15); 2.61–2.53 (m, 2H, 16); 2.33–2.26 (m, 1H, 17); 2.19–2.14 (m, 1H, 17); 2.05–1.98 (m, 2H, 18); 0.99 (t, 3H, ³J (H,H) = 7.6 Hz, 19). DEPTQ spectrum (CDCl₃, 151 MHz, rt): δ [ppm] = 172.2 (20); 167.7 (21); 162.7 (d, J_{C-F} = 247 Hz, 22); 157.5 (23); 152.5 (24); 149.0 (25); 146.5 (26); 146.0 (27); 132.4 (28); 131.3 (1); 130.8 (4); 130.3 (d, J_{C-F} = 8.2 Hz, 6); 129.8 (2); 128.6 (29); 128.4 (3); 128.3 (30); 128.2 (5); 120.5 (31); 115.6 (d, J_{C-F} = 21.5 Hz, 8); 96.0 (7); 76.2 (32); 69.0 (13); 67.3 (9); 66.9 (11); 64.6 (14); 50.1 (10); 32.0 (17); 31.1 (16); 23.7 (18); 7.7 (19). Signals corresponding to carbon atoms 12, 15, 33 and 34 were not detectable. HRMS (APPI, CH₂Cl₂): calcd. for C₄₂H₃₇FFeN₃O₇ [M + H]⁺ (m/z): 770.1959 found: 770.1964. Elemental C, H, N analysis: calcd (%) for C₄₂H₃₆FFeN₃O₇•EtOAc: C 64.34, H 5.28, N 4.89; found: C 64.75, H 5.29, N 5.08. Characterization data: Figures S37–S43, Supporting Information.

4.2. Properties of Prodrugs in Cell Free Settings

4.2.1. Solubility in Aqueous Buffers

Prodrug **C** was dissolved in DMSO at concentrations of 5, 2.5, 1 and 0.5 mM. These solutions (10 μL) were transferred to quartz cuvettes with either triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) buffer (0.1 M, 990 μL) or Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 Medium (990 μL) containing fetal bovine serum (FBS, 5%, m/v) and mixed thoroughly at 22 °C to obtain solutions/suspensions of compounds at final concentrations of 50, 25, 10 and 5 μM. Mixtures appearing transparent were considered as true solutions. This was the case for the concentrations 5 and 10 μM.

4.2.2. Prodrug Aggregation State in Aqueous Buffers

UV-visible spectroscopy: UV-visible spectra of prodrug **C** in TEAA and RPMI media were acquired at 22 ± 2 °C. Absorbances at 789 nm and 340 nm observed were plotted as a function of the concentration of the compound. True solutions containing monomeric prodrug **C** were not expected to absorb light at 789 nm. Moreover, their absorbance at 340 nm was expected to linearly depend on the concentration of prodrug **C** (Beer's law).

Dynamic light scattering (DLS): DLS was measured with a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Red badge, ZEN3600, Malvern Panalytical Ltd.) by using disposable cuvettes (polystyrene) with a sample volume of 2.5 mL. DLS of solutions/suspensions of prodrugs **B** and **C** (1 μM, 5 μM, 10 μM, 15 μM, 25 μM) in RPMI 1640 Medium containing FBS (5%, v/v) and DMSO (1 %, v/v) were determined under the following

settings: 22 ± 2 °C, solvent: water (RI: 1.330; viscosity (cP): 0.6864); analysis: (RI: 1.45; material absorption: 0.001); backward scatter; 3 measurements per sample).

4.2.3. *N*-Octanol/Water Partition Coefficients (LogP Values)

Reversed-phase (RP)-thin layer chromatography (TLC) plates from Macherey–Nagel (Alugram, Aluminiumfolien RP-18 W/UV₂₅₄, stationary phase thickness: 0.15 mm) were used for determination of *n*-octanol/water partition coefficients (LogP values). Mixtures of aqueous 3-(*N*-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid buffer (MOPS, 100 mM, pH 7.4) and acetonitrile (5/8 and 2/3 in both cases: v/v) were used as eluents. Benzophenone (LogP = 3.18), anthracene (LogP = 4.50), pyrene (LogP = 4.88) and perylene (LogP = 6.25) were used as reference compounds with known LogP values. Freshly prepared solutions of the samples and references (in CH₂Cl₂) were spotted on the RP-TLC plates. The solvent migration distance was $L = 4.5$ cm. The spots of the compounds were monitored by using UV-imaging. Each spot was marked and its position relative to the start line (L_c) was measured. R_f values were calculated as ratio of L_c to L . Calibration plots of R_f versus logP values for the known compounds were used for determination of logP values of new compounds.

4.2.4. Monitoring Activation of Prodrugs in the Presence of H₂O₂

Fluorescence spectroscopy: Prodrugs B and C (10 μM) were dissolved in TEAA buffer (pH = 7.4 containing DMSO, 1%, v/v) and fluorescence spectra were acquired ($\lambda_{ex} = 365$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 436$ nm) every 30 min on a Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, Germany) using fluorescence cuvettes (Hellma GmbH, Germany) with a sample volume of 1 mL. The samples were incubated with H₂O₂ (2 mM) for 60 min.

LC-UV-MS: Prodrugs B or C (20 μM) were dissolved in TEAA buffer (100 mM, pH 7, 8) containing acetonitrile (25 %, v/v), DMSO (1%, v/v) and either H₂O₂ (10 mM) or without it. The resulting mixture was gently shaken for various time points. The samples (20 μL) were analysed by LC-UV-MS. Separation conditions: column – Macherey–Nagel EC HPLC NUCLEODUR C18 HTec, particle size 5 μm of the stationary phase, column size: 50 × 2 mm; the column was coupled to a UV detector (detection of light absorbance at 330 nm) and to a quadrupole MS detector (detection of total positive ion current); two different gradients of solvent B in solvent A were used (solvent A: ammonium formate in water (10 mM) containing formic acid (0.1%, v/v); solvent B: CH₃CN containing formic acid (0.1%, v/v)): *gradient A*–15% B, then from 15 to 95% B in 11 min, followed by 4 min at 95% B; *gradient B*–15% B, then from 15 to 50% in 11 min, then from 50 to 95% in 30 s, followed by 4 min at 95% B.

4.3. Cell Culture Experiments

4.3.1. Cells and Cell Culturing

Human ovarian cancer cell line A2780 was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Acute monocytic leukemia THP-1 cell line was kindly provided by the collaborating laboratory of Prof. Dr. C. Alexiou, SEON, University Hospital Erlangen. Human lung fibroblast GM01379 cell line was provided by Prof. Dr. Ivana Ivanović-Burmazović (Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich). A2780 and THP-1 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium containing 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (m/v), 1% GlutaMAX (m/v) and 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin (Pen/Strep, m/v). A2780 cells were grown to 80%–90% confluence, while suspension cell line THP-1 was cultured to 0.5 – 1.5×10^6 cells/mL and diluted as

required. GM01379 cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% FBS (m/v), 1% GlutaMAX (m/v) and 1% Pen/Strep (m/v) to 80%–90% confluence. For passaging and experimental setup, adherent cells were detached from culture flasks by using a mixture of trypsin/EDTA (0.25%, v/v) in Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (DPBS). The fluorescence of living cells was quantified using CytoFlex flow cytometer from Beckman Coulter, Inc. The data were processed using the inCyte™ software package from Merck Millipore and ModFit LT 4.1 software from Verity Software House.

4.3.2. Determination of Mitochondrial ROS (mROS) Level in A2780, THP1, and GM01379 Cells

The cells were seeded in a 96-microtiter plate at the following concentrations–A2780: 250 cells/μL, THP-1: 300 cells/μL, GM01379: 125 cells/μL using mentioned above cell culture media. The cells were left standing overnight at 37 °C in an atmosphere with 5% CO₂ and 95% humidity. The supernatant was removed and substituted with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS, 100 μL/well) containing MitoSOX Red Superoxide Indicator (0.1% DMSO, 5 μM) and incubated for 20 min in the dark at 37 °C. Next, the cells were washed twice and detached from the microtiter plate using a mixture of trypsin/EDTA. After resuspending in the corresponding cell culture medium, all cells were transferred to a U shaped 96-well microtiter plate to measure the fluorescence of each cell by the flow cytometer CytoFLEX (Beckman Coulter) at excitation $\lambda_{ex} = 488$ nm and emission $\lambda_{em} = 585 \pm 42$ nm. This experiment was repeated three times (N = 3). The average cell surface area of the cells was determined by a Zeiss Axio Observer (objective: 40x/1.30 Oil DIC). The data were processed with Fiji ImageJ software. The average the cell surface area for at least 10 cells was determined (N = 10). The mROS level (Figure 4A) was expressed as the MitoSOX fluorescence divided by the cell surface area. For statistical analysis, unpaired Student's t-test was conducted.

4.3.3. Fluorescence Microscopy

A2780 cells (80 cells/μL, in 500 μL RPMI 1640 medium containing 5% FBS, 1% Gln, and 1% Pen/Strep) were seeded in 35 mm imaging dish (μ-Dish 35 mm, high, ibidi GmbH, Germany) and allowed to attach overnight at 37°C and 5% CO₂. The next day, the cells were washed and pre-incubated with the mitochondria labeling dye rhodamine 123 (R123, 1 μM, in Hank's buffered salt solution, HBSS, 2 mL/dish) and incubated for 20 min. The cells were then washed twice with DPBS (Dulbecco's buffered saline, 2mL/dish) and covered with fresh medium once with and once without *N*-acetyl cysteine (NAC, 1 mM) and incubated for a further hour. After washing again with DPBS, fresh medium (2 mL/dish) was added to the cells and were treated with the prodrug C (10 μM, 1% DMSO, v/v) for 1h. After an additional washing step a fresh portion of the medium was added to the cells before imaging with a Zeiss AX10 Lab A1. The prodrug C–derived fluorescent products were detected at $\lambda_{ex} = 365$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 420$ – 470 nm (blue channel). R123 was detected at $\lambda_{ex} = 430$ – 510 nm and $\lambda_{em} = 475$ – 575 nm (green channel).

4.3.4. Evaluation of Cell Viability by MTT Assay

Adherent A2780 and GM01379 cells were washed twice with DPBS, detached, resuspended, diluted to required concentrations and seeded in 96-microtiter plates: A2780 cells–125 cells/μL in RPMI 1640 containing 10% FBS, 1% GlutaMAX and 1% Pen/Strep; GM01379 cells–100 cells/μL in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% GlutaMAX

and 1% Pen/Strep. Suspension cells THP-1 were washed twice via centrifugation (180 rcf, 5 min), diluted to 300 cells/ μL in the supplemented RPMI 1640 medium. After incubation overnight in a 37 °C chamber containing 5% CO_2 and 95% humidity, stock solutions of investigated compounds in DMSO were prepared and subsequently added to the cells (1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{well}$; 1% DMSO, v/v). Each condition was tested in triplicates ($N = 3$). After incubation for 72 h at 37 °C, 95% humidity and 5% CO_2 , a solution of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazoliumbromide (MTT; 5 mg/mL in DPBS; 20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{well}$) was added and the cells were incubated for further 3 h. Next, the cells were treated with sodium dodecyl sulfate solution (SDS; 10%; m/m solution in 0.01 M aqueous HCl; 90 $\mu\text{L}/\text{well}$) and incubated overnight. The next day, absorbance intensity of the mixtures at 590 nm was measured using the microplate reader (Varioskan LUX Multimode Microplate Reader from ThermoScientific). The absorbance intensity at 690 nm was used as a baseline value.

4.3.5. Effect of the Prodrug on Cell Cycle of A2780 Cells

A2780 cells were seeded in a 6-well microtiter plate at a density of 200 cells/ μL in solution containing FBS (5%, v/v), GlutaMAX (1%, v/v), Pen/Strep (1%, v/v) (total volume 2.5 mL). The next day, the cells were washed twice with DPBS (2.5 mL per well) and fresh RPMI 1640 medium (2 mL) as well as the prodrug **C** (250 nM), drug **cpt-OH** (20 nM) (both dissolved in DMSO, 20 μL) and DMSO carrier (1%, v/v) were added. Three technical replicates were prepared per sample and pure DMSO served as a negative control. After 48 h incubation, the cells were washed twice with DPBS, detached from the microtiter plate with the above-described trypsin/EDTA mixture (0.5 mL), resuspended in growth medium (5% FBS, 1 mL) and transferred into 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes. The cells were pelleted by centrifugation for 5 min at 113 rcf and the pellet was washed with DPBS (0.5 mL). After centrifugation under the same conditions, the cells were re-suspended in DPBS (4 °C, 0.4 mL). Subsequently, ice-cold ethanol (0.8 mL) was added to each sample dropwise for 1 min during gentle shaking. For fixation and membrane permeabilization, the samples were incubated for 2 h at 4 °C in the dark. The cells were once again pelleted and washed with DPBS (0.5 mL), before resuspension in PI staining solution (0.2 mL: 20 μg RNase A, 10 μg propidium iodide (PI) in DPBS) and incubation for 30 min at 37 °C. Afterwards, the cells were gently resuspended and diluted with DPBS (0.2 mL). The fluorescence of the DNA-intercalated PI was measured by a CytoFLEX S Flow Cytometer (Beckman Coulter) at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 480\text{--}496$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 543\text{--}627$ nm. For data evaluation, the ModFit LT 4.1 software from Verity Software House was used.

4.4. In Vivo Experiment

These studies were conducted as previously described for prodrug **B**.^[7] Prodrug **C** was dissolved in the DMF/PEG400 carrier. Mice were injected (subcutaneous injection, 12mg/kg) at day 0, 3 and 6 and analyzed at day 7 for changes in blood counts with an automated hemocounter (ABX Pentra 80, Horiba) and/or bone marrow myeloid, lymphoid and progenitor cells by flow cytometry. For BM analysis, we euthanized mice with CO_2 and collected femurs. We flushed femurs with 1 mL PEB (PBS 1x, EDTA 0.5M, FBS 0.5%) into an Eppendorf tube. The cell suspension was centrifuged for 5 min, 1500 rpm, 4 °C, and the pellet was resuspended in RBC 1x Lysis Buffer for 5 min at 22 °C and washed again with PEB buffer. Then, we stained a fraction of the single-cell suspensions from femurs of mice with biotin-conjugated anti-CD3e/CD11b/Gr-1/Ter119/CD45R (Lineage markers or LIN) (1:100) APC-conjugated anti-Sca1 (1:200) and PerCP-Cy5.5-conjugated anti-cKit (1:200) for analysis of BM progenitor

cells; and with BV786-conjugated anti-CD45 (1:200), PerCP-Cy5.5-conjugated anti-CXCR2 (1:200), AF647-conjugated anti-Ly6G (1:200), BV510-conjugated anti-CD11b (1:200), PE Cy7-conjugated anti-CD3e and APC Cy7-conjugated anti-CD45R for analysis of BM myeloid and lymphoid cells. Primary staining was performed for 30 min at 4 °C. After washing, we incubated the cells with Streptavidin-PE Cy7 (1:300) for 15 min at 4 °C. Cytometric analysis was performed using a LSRII Fortessa (BD Biosciences) analyzer. We estimated the total numbers of these different cell populations with PEB/DAPI buffer containing true count beads (BD Biosciences). Data were then analysed with FlowJo (FlowJo LLC, Ashland, OR) software. For identification of BM progenitor cells, after exclusion of cell doublets and dead cells with DAPI (1:10000), myeloid progenitors (MP) were identified as $\text{LIN}^{\text{NEG}}\text{Sca1}^{\text{NEG}}\text{cKit}^+$ and LSK as $\text{LIN}^{\text{NEG}}\text{Sca1}^+\text{cKit}^+$. Mature neutrophils were identified as $\text{CD45}^+\text{CD11b}^+\text{Ly6G}^+\text{CXCR2}^{\text{high}}$, immature neutrophils as $\text{CD45}^+\text{CD11b}^+\text{Ly6G}^+\text{CXCR2}^{\text{low}}$, monocytes as $\text{CD45}^+\text{CD11b}^+\text{Ly6G}^{\text{NEG}}$, B cells as $\text{CD45}^+\text{CD11b}^{\text{NEG}}\text{CD45R}^+$ and T cells as $\text{CD45}^+\text{CD11b}^{\text{NEG}}\text{CD3e}^+$. While the experiment, the mice were weighted and evaluated for physical appearance every day, and for organ appearance the day of the sacrifice. The control group was injected with the carrier.

The in vivo experiments were performed in 7- to 16-week-old male mice in a C57BL/6 genetic background. The mice were kept in a specific pathogen-free facility at Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Cardiovasculares (CNIC) under a 12 h light/12 h darkness schedule (lights on at 7am, off at 7pm), with water and chow available ad libitum. All experimental procedures were approved by the Animal Care and Ethics Committee of CNIC and the regional authorities (PROEX 101/18 // PROEX 194.2/21).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

We thank the European Commission (861878–NeuroCure) for funding this study. Few precursors used in this work were prepared by Ms. Elisabeth Masson and Mr. Silvan Stein via standard protocols.

Open access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

Keywords: Aminoferrrocene · Anticancer · Catalysis · Mitochondria · Reactive oxygen species

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Manuscript received: January 12, 2025

Revised manuscript received: February 27, 2025

Accepted manuscript online: March 24, 2025

Version of record online: April 28, 2025